

Role of Yoga Prana Vidya system in treatment and healing of Musculo-skeletal problems: A multiple case study of human patients

Leelavathi Nayak

YPV certified healer and trainer, Mangalore, India

***Venkata Satyanarayana Nanduri**

Consultant, Research & Publications, Yoga Prana Vidya Ashram, Sri Ramana Trust, Thally-635118, Krishnagiri District, Tamilnadu.

*Corresponding author Email: vsnanduri@yahoo.com

Abstract

Introduction: Musculo-skeletal disorders (MSDs) are highly prevalent globally with 1.71 billion people in 160 countries, and patients need rehabilitation therapies to recover. This paper presents four cases of MSD that were healed successfully using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) protocols.

Method: This is a case study method, and the process of investigation consists of going through the case details of each patient and the healer's records.

Results: A review of these four cases indicate that the patients recovered from their Musculo-skeletal conditions within 2 to 4 weeks of healing done daily, using YPV advanced treatment protocols.

Conclusions: Being no-drug no-touch method of energy healing, YPV offers great scope in the treatment of MSD conditions as alternative low-cost treatment modality. Recommendations include looking into the possibilities of training doctors, nurses and other healthcare workers in the practice of YPV healing system, and conduct further research on the application of YPV in treating MSDs using appropriate sample size and methodology.

Key words: Musculo-Skeletal Disorders (MSD), Therapy, Rehabilitation, Yoga Prana Vidya System®, YPV®

I. Introduction

Musculoskeletal Conditions

The prevalence of musculoskeletal conditions varies by diagnosis and age factors, and people of all ages globally are affected. [1] Musculoskeletal conditions are among the leading contributors to disability, and cause limitation in the mobility and dexterity of those affected, with possibilities of consequent early retirement from work, lower

levels of well-being and reduced ability to participate in society. [2] Low back pain is the single leading cause of disability in 160 countries. Because of population increases and ageing, the number of people with musculoskeletal conditions is rapidly increasing. The disability associated with musculoskeletal conditions is projected to continue to increase in the near future, and consequently the highest contributor to the global need for rehabilitation services. [1]. Other contributors to the overall burden of musculoskeletal conditions include fractures with 436 million people globally, osteoarthritis (343 million), other injuries (305 million), neck pain (222 million), amputations (175 million) and rheumatoid arthritis (14 million). [2].

Musculoskeletal conditions include conditions that affect:

- joints, such as osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, psoriatic arthritis, gout, ankylosing spondylitis;
- bones, such as osteoporosis, osteopenia and associated fragility fractures, traumatic fractures;
- muscles, such as sarcopenia;
- the spine, such as back and neck pain;
- multiple body areas or systems, such as regional and widespread pain disorders and inflammatory diseases such as connective tissue diseases, ligament tears and vasculitis that have musculoskeletal manifestations, for example systemic lupus erythematosus.

A recent analysis of Global Burden of Disease (GBD) data showed that approximately 1.71 billion people globally have musculoskeletal conditions (2). Commonly used therapies are rehabilitation therapies which are actions of restoring someone to health or normal life through training and therapeutic techniques after events such as accidents, illness or addiction.

Yoga Prana Vidya System

The broad concept of Yoga has to be viewed and understood, while Yoga in recent times is being used only to refer to Asanas or postures of physical exercises and sometimes even to pranayama or a form of systematic breathing exercise. These are in fact parts of Yoga and not the complete Yoga. Yoga as propounded by Yogi Patanjali, is actually known as Ashtanga Yoga consisting of 8 steps and each of the steps is equally very important. There are many levels of Yoga in practice.

As per the ancient Yogic teachings, the physical body is an important vehicle of the Soul for use in the physical world and it must be maintained, sustained and used for the purpose of the Divine. The purpose of yoga is to achieve union of the soul with the Divine and manifest its greatness on Earth. The Soul (referring here to the Incarnated Soul or the Jeevatma) has 3 vehicles through which it operates and are interconnected:

1. The Energy Body known as Pranamaya Kosha, including Physical body known as Annamaya Kosha.
2. The Emotional Body or the Kama Kosha
3. The Mental Body or the Manomaya Kosha
4. Importantly, brain is the instrument of the mind which includes all the above three vehicles. Mind itself is the instrument of the Soul

In addition to treating the physical body, it is also important to maintain healthy state of the energy body (also known as etheric body) in order to sustain, maintain or regain good health. Anything that happens to the physical body, also affects the Etheric Body. The Prana is Life Force or Energy used for the maintenance of the energy body and Vidya is the know-how. The technology of maintaining the energy body is therefore termed Yoga Prana Vidya (or YPV) system which offers integrated and holistic techniques for maintaining both physical and energy bodies and also maintain the etheric connectivity with the higher self.

Healing is the process by which the energy body can be renewed thus bringing beneficial changes in the physical

body. Used up energy or diseased energy can be removed and the energy body can be charged with fresh energy. All biological life on earth has the ability to heal itself. Energy follows thought and energy accelerates the healing process. Healing involves two steps: (1) Cleansing, or removing the used-up energy and (2) Energizing, or giving fresh energy.

In YPV, the healer thus becomes a channel of energy, who receives and transfers energy. Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) is a revolutionary form of energy "medicine". It is based on ancient science and art that has been revived in a new form which is easily adaptable and is compatible with busy life in modern world. A healer can heal him/herself besides healing others. There are two modes of YPV healing. In one mode, a healer heals the other person seated in the same room, which is known as proximal healing. In the other mode known as distal healing, a healer is situated at a place away from the patient, and healing energy can be sent distantly and instantly through inter-connection with and through the earth's energy body. During pandemic times such as COVID, distal healing had been effectively the main mode used to deliver healing energies to all needed patients situated hundreds or even thousands of kilometers away.

Literature shows about 50 published research articles based on documented medical and psychological cases revealing that YPV healing system has been successfully applied in the management and control of various illness conditions which include for example:

Diabetes, Blood pressure and heart ailments, ENT and respiratory ailments, Musculoskeletal, First aid and emergency cases, Dental cases, Eye camps and Healing camps, Cancer cases, Digestive disorders, Multiple disorders, kidney function, prostate function, Psychological cases like anxiety, depression, suicidal tendencies, relationship issues, lack of attention and concentration, academic performance, improving mentally retarded children's condition, Criminal tendencies, Cases of substance abuse and addiction, COVID cases etc. [3-23].

The YPV system protocols have been found effective as complementary and also as alternative mode of treatment. This paper presents four documented cases of Skeletal muscular problems healed by a healer using YPV protocols as alternative medicine successfully.

II. Case series

The following four Musculo-Skeletal cases were treated using YPV healing techniques.

Case 1: A male patient of 39 years, unconscious SAH patient (subarachnoid Hemorrhage) with pressure injury ulcer due to foot splint to prevent foot drop.

YPV Healing started on 24/4/2016 to the patient. Affected parts (Figure 1) cleansed with green and orange colour prana, and energised with orange-red twice a day. Later on energised with green and red prana twice a day. Minor chakrams of legs, sex chakram, navel chakram and Basic chakram cleansed with green and orange and energised with white prana. Blood cleansing done and all the chakrams were balanced during healing. A session of 20 minutes of healing was given twice daily. Day by day the wound started filling up and completely healed within one month of healing.

Fig 1

Case 2: A female patient of 51 years who fell down from a 2-wheeler vehicle and not able to walk because of pain and swelling. (Figure 2)

YPV Healing started on 28/03/22 to her left leg ankle. Affected parts cleansed with green and orange and energised with greenish-blue and violet and later by green and bluish-violet to the ankle. Affected chakrams of legs, sex chakram, Basic chakram and navel chakram cleansed and strengthened. All the chakrams balanced during healing. A session of 20 minutes of healing was given twice daily. Day by day pain and swelling reduced and the patient completely recovered within 10days of healings.

Figure 2

Case 3: A female patient 35 years aged, had ankle sprain during November 2015, and was not able to walk because of pain and swollen ankle. (Figure 3)

YPV Healing started to Affected parts. Cleansed with green and orange and energised with greenish-blue and violet and later green and bluish-violet to the ankle. Affected chakrams of legs and other related chakrams cleansed, strengthened and all the chakrams were balanced during Healing. A session of 20 minutes of healing was given twice daily. Pain and swelling reduced gradually and the patient completely recovered within about 2 weeks of healings.

Figure 3

Case 4: A Male patient of 75 years suffered hip injury from a fall. X-Ray showed no bone fractures. The muscles were sprained and pain was severe, and the patient was unable to sit or sleep properly.

Healing started on 8th Jan 2022 with YPV level 3 healing (psychotherapy) daily once and level 2 healing using color pranas to affected parts and chakrams twice daily. Blood cleansing done and balanced all the chakrams during healing. The Basic chakram, sex chakram, perineum chakram, hip minor chakrams, navel chakrams and minor chakrams of legs cleansed with green and orange prana strengthened with red prana. Spine is cleansed and strengthened. Affected parts are cleansed with green and orange prana and energised with green and bluish-violet prana. Hip minor chakras cleansed with green and orange and energised with white prana. A session of 20 minutes of healing was given twice daily for one week. Pain started reducing gradually day by day. Healing continued by cleansing and energising affected parts daily once. Within one month of healing, the patient completely recovered.

III. Discussion

Within the limited literature available on the topic of Complementary and Alternative Medicine for MSD (Musculo-skeletal disorders) some studies have stated use of acupressure, acupuncture and Yoga. A review study on the use of Yoga for MSD by McCaffrey and Park [24] found that, Of the 31 identified studies, 15 used RCT methodology. Based on the outcomes of these 15 RCT trials, yoga programs were demonstrated to be safe for use and feasible to be delivered to people with musculoskeletal disorders. The reviewed studies reported duration of yoga sessions from 8 weeks to 12 weeks, each session lasting 45 to 90 minutes, once or twice a week. Another study by Koneru and Tanikonda stated that Yoga was found to be more effective in treatment of MSDs than other modes of physical activities. [25].

From the study of these four cases documented in this article, it is observed that YPV healing worked well as rehabilitation therapy to alleviate pain of the patients affected by MSDs.

IV. Conclusions

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) system and its protocols have been found to be effective in a variety of health conditions both as complementary and alternative medicine in the treatment and normalization of patients. It is recommended that all healthcare workers including Doctors and Nurses should learn and practice safe and established Energy healing techniques such as YPV to help patients recover without medication. There is vast scope to conduct further studies using appropriate sample size and methodologies to document the outcomes of YPV healing techniques to treat Musculo-Skeletal Disorders.

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